

Alchi temple complex

also known as “Alchi Chokhor”, “Alchi monastery”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Religious Place, Monument, Temple, Religious Complex, shrines, Tibetan Buddhism, Tantric Buddhism, South Asian Religion, Religious Practice

The Alchi temple complex is one of the earliest and most culturally significant (wc) Buddhist sites in the western Himalayas. It is located in the Leh district of Ladakh in the present-day state of Jammu-Kashmir, India. The site consists of five temples and several stupas (chörtens) built between the eleventh/thirteenth and fourteenth centuries. This was a period of political fragmentation and declining religious patronage in the kingdom of Tibeta, based in the central Tibetan plateau. As a result, the western Himalayas (Ngari) arose as the dominant political and religious authority. It also was an important nexus of trade and pilgrimage routes from neighboring Kashmir and central Tibet. During this period, religious and political elites sponsored production of new temples and monasteries in the region. These structures have become a primary trove for studying the period since there are few extant textual sources. The Alchi complex's earliest two temples—called the Dukhang (“Assembly Hall”) and the Sumtsek (a three-storeyed temple) — were built shortly after this shift in power and provide valuable information about religious, political, and social aspects of the day. Local tradition holds that the Dukhang is one of 108 temples built under the auspices of renowned translator Lotsawa Rinchen Zangpo (958-1055). The date of the Sumtsek is the subject of ongoing scholarly debate. Some scholars posit an 11th-century date, whereas argue that it was built in the 13th century. A painted panel depicting the nascent Drigung Kagyu lineage is central to this debate. There is a general consensus, however, that the Dukhang was built shortly before the Sumtsek. Each temple contains an inscription naming the temple's founder. The Dukhang was founded by Kalden Sherab and the Sumtsek was founded by Tsultrim Ö, both members of the ruling Dro clan. The Dukhang and Sumtsek, as well as neighboring Sumda and Mangyu temples, share thematic and stylistic features. Collectively, these temples are called “The Alchi group.” These temples' architecture is typical of central Tibetan structures, but their interior murals and sculptures are executed in a Kashmiri style, suggesting the artists were themselves Kashmiri. As such, the murals are a rare example of surviving Kashmiri painting. In addition to the overall Buddhist iconographic program, the murals depict patrons, devotees, and textiles which elucidate the material, cultural, and economic makeup of this well-connected political and religious authority. Today, Alchi is no longer an active monastery, but continues to draw pilgrims and tourists alike.

Date Range: 950 CE - 1500 CE

Region: Alchi village

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Himalayas

The Alchi temple complex is located in a village of the same name in the Leh district of Ladakh in the present-day state of Jammu-Kashmir, India. Alchi lies next to the Indus River and is surrounded by mountains of the Karakoram Range.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Goepper, Roger and Jaroslav Poncar. *Alchi: Ladakh's Hidden Buddhist Sanctuary*. London: Serindia, 1996.
- Source 2: Luczanits, Christian. "The early Buddhist Heritage of Ladakh Reconsidered." *Ladakhi Histories: Local and Regional Perspectives*, Brill's Tibetan Studies Library Vol. 9. Edited by Henk Blezer, Alex McKay, and Charles Ramble, 65-96. Leiden: Brill, 2005.
- Source 3: Snellgrove, David L. and Tadeusz Skorupski. *The Cultural Heritage of Ladakh*, 2 vols. Boulder: Prajña Press, 1977.
- Source 1: Luczanits, Christian and Holger Neuwirth. "The Development of the Alchi Temple Complex. An Interdisciplinary Approach." In *Heritage Conservation and Research in India. 60 years of Indo-Austrian collaboration*, Konservierungswissenschaft, Restaurierung, Technologie, 6. Edited by Gabriela Krist and Tatjana Bayerová, 79-84. Wien, Weimar: Böhlau, 2010.
- Source 2: Luczanits, Christian. *Buddhist Sculpture in Clay: Early Western Himalayan Art, late 10th to early 13th centuries* Chicago: Serindia, 2004.
- Source 3: van Ham, Peter, ed. *Heavenly Himalayas: The Murals of Mangyu and Other Discoveries in Ladakh*. Munich: Prestel, 2010.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.luczanits.net/index.html>
- Source 1 Description: This is Christian Luczanits' professional website. Luczanits has documented, researched, and published on Alchi and "The Alchi Group" for more than two decades. His website includes general introductions to Alchi and related sites, photographs, and a list of his publications on the subject.
- Source 2 URL: <https://whav.aussereurop.univie.ac.at/ic/162/>
- Source 2 Description: The Western Himalayan Archive Vienna is a digital archive of photographs from across the western Himalayan region. The archive has an extensive collection of photographs of Alchi and related monuments. These images are invaluable for understanding textual research on the site.
- Source 3 URL: <https://archresearch.tugraz.at/results/alchi/>
- Source 3 Description: The Graz University of Technology's research project "Buddhist Architecture in the Himalayas" produced extensive 2D and 3D models of the Alchi complex as a whole, as well as each component part. These models illustrate the temples' layout, spatial relations, and elevations.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Alchi village is located in the Leh district of Ladakh. The district's capital Leh is the largest town in Ladakh and comprises 21 wards, 113 villages, and a total population of 30, 870, according to the 2011 Census of India. Alchi village is located approximately 70km from Leh along the banks of the Indus River. The village comprises 145 households with a population of 932 according to the 2011 Census of India. Historically, this was primarily an agricultural area but, in recent decades, increasingly depends on the tourist industry.

Reference: Indian Government. "district of Leh Government Website", n.d.. <https://leh.nic.in/>.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Alchi is approximately 4.5 km from Lardo village, 6 km from Saspol village, and 16.5 km from Basgo village.

Reference: Indian Government, and Ladakh Autonomous Hill Development Council, Leh. "map of District". District Leh - Ladakh, n.d.. <https://leh.nic.in/about-district/map-of-district/>.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Historically, Alchi was primarily reachable by foot. Presently, the village is easily accessible by car, bus, or motorbike. Some scholars have argued that Alchi has been studied significantly more than the other two temples in "The Alchi Group" (Sumda Chung and Mangyu) because it more accessible. The other two temples are not accessible by motorable roads. However, local pilgrims traveling on foot (who are acclimatized to the high altitude and harsh conditions of the Himalayan mountains) can visit Alchi, Sumda Chung, and Mangyu in one or two days. The art historian Rob Linrothe confirmed the relative proximity of these sites by completing this journey himself.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian. *Buddhist Sculpture in Clay: Early Western Himalayan Art, Late 10th to Early 13th Centuries*. Chicago: Serindia, 2004.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: Certain parts of the temples and stupas have been restored but the buildings themselves are original.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the temples' paintings and sculptures include non-human beings with supernatural powers, such as the Makara (a mythological aquatic hybrid creature), Garuda (a mythological bird-like creature) and Nagas (serpent deities). However, these beings are not the primary focus of worship. Rather, they are typically depicted as vehicles, supports, or attendants for Buddhas and bodhisattvas.

Reference: Beer, Robert. *The Handbook of Tibetan Buddhist Symbols*. Boston: Shambala, 2003.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The temples are dedicated to multiple supernatural beings, such as Buddhas and bodhisattvas. Yet, certain components of the overall iconographic plan are centered on a specific Buddha or bodhisattva. For example, clay sculptures in the central niche of the Dukhang are arranged in a Vajradhātu mandala centered on the primordial buddha Vairocana.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian. *Buddhist Sculpture in Clay: Early Western Himalayan Art, Late 10th to Early 13th Centuries*. Chicago: Serindia, 2004.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The temples are dedicated to a range of Buddhas and bodhisattvas.

Notes: The temples' iconography is quite complex, particularly the Dukhang and Sumtsek. In the Dukhang, the wall paintings include seven mandalas from the Yoga Tantras, each

comprised of numerous deities surrounding a specific Buddha or bodhisattva. For example, the Sarvavid mandala centers on Vairocana, the primordial buddha, and the Dharmadhātu mandala centers on Manjusri, the bodhisattva of wisdom. Clay sculptures in the central niche (and therefore the temple's primary focal point) are arranged in a Vajradhātu mandala with a four-headed Vairocana at the center. The murals also depict other supernatural beings. For example, the central niche is flanked by 1000 painted Buddhas. Below these Buddhas is a depiction of the Buddha Akṣobhya in his paradise (called Abhirati). The three-storey Sumtsek is even more elaborate than the Dukhang. The temple interior is square with niches on three sides. In addition to wall paintings, each niche contains a monumental clay sculpture. Manjusri (the bodhisattva of wisdom) is in the left niche, Maitreya (the future Buddha) is in the central niche directly opposite the entrance, and Avalokitesvara (the bodhisattva of compassion) is in the right niche. The Sumtsek's wall paintings include depictions of various bodhisattvas and goddesses, such as Tara/Prajnaparamita (identity is debated) and Manjusri. A painted panel over the entrance depicts protector deities, such as Mahākāla.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian. *Buddhist Sculpture in Clay: Early Western Himalayan Art, Late 10th to Early 13th Centuries*. Chicago: Serindia, 2004.

Reference: Rohilla, Jyoti. "green Tārā in the Wall Paintings of Alchi". In *Sacred Geography of Goddesses in South Asia: Essays in Memory of David Kinsley*, edited by Rana P.B. Singh. Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2010.

Reference: Tribe, Anthony. "mañjuśrī as Adibuddha: The Identity of an Eight-armed Form of Mañjuśrī Found in Early Western Himalayan Buddhist Art in the Light of Three Nāmasaṃgīti-related Texts". In *Śaivism and the Tantric Traditions: Essays in Honour of Alexis G.J.S. Sanderson*, edited by Dominic Goodall, Shaman Hatley, Harunaga Isaacson, and Srilata Raman. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

Reference: Linrothe, Rob. "mapping the Iconographic Programme of the Sumtsek". In *Alchi, Ladakh's Hidden Buddhist Sanctuary: The Sumtsek*, edited by Roger Goeppe and Jaroslav Poncar. London: Serindia, 1996.

Reference: Linrothe, Rob. "talisman, Reliquary and Instrument of Enlightenment: The Alchi Sumtsek as a Mandalic Site". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 22–29.

Reference: Goeppe, Roger. "murals in the Early Temples of Alchi". In *On the Path to Void: Buddhist Art of the Tibetan Realm*, edited by Pratapaditya Pal. Mumbai: Marg, 1996.

Reference: Goeppe, Roger. "akshobhya and His Paradise: Murals in the Dukhang of Alchi". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 16–21.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian. "alchi, Ladakh", n.d.. <http://www.luczanits.net/sites/Alchi.html>.

Reference: N/A. "alchi". *Western Himalaya Archive Vienna*, n.d.. <https://whav.aussereurop.univie.ac.at/ic/4514/>.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

— Yes

Notes: In Tibetan Buddhism, enlightened masters are regarded as exceptional figures with supramundane powers.

Reference: Linrothe, Rob, and Henrik Sorenson. "group Portrait: Mahasiddhas in the Alchi Sumtsek". In *Embodying Wisdom: Art, Text, and Interpretation in the History of Esoteric Buddhism*, edited by Rob

Linrothe. Copenhagen: Seminar for Buddhist Studies, 2001.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The high quality of the architectural construction, paintings, sculptures, and wood-carving indicate that they were produced by master craftspeople. There is no historical record of unskilled laborers working at the site but it is quite possible that an additional workforce was used.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

- ↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:
– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: The Alchi complex served multiple purposes. Some temples include an assembly hall where monastics would gather for rituals. The small size and general layout of certain temples indicate that they were used for individual meditation, contemplation, or circumambulation. The complex as a whole, and its component part, generate merit for and bestow blessings upon devotees.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- Yes

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– No

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

- Yes

Notes: The Alchi complex's temples and stupas are built with natural materials using methods typical

of the region. The temples are built with stone and mud mortar and finished with a coat of mud plaster. Verandas, doorways, ceilings, and interior columns are made from wood. Stone is often used for flooring, especially in verandas. In the interior, many of the sculptures are made from clay. The murals and sculptures are painted with ground mineral pigments. Some also use gold. The stupas are primarily mud plaster applied over a wooden frame. The paintings also use mineral pigments.

Reference: Gill, Maninder Singh, Carolina Priego Rendo, and Sreekumar Menon. "Materials and Techniques: Early Buddhist Wall Paintings and Sculptures at Sumda Chun, Ladakh". *Studies in Conservation* 59, no. 5 (2014): 300–313.

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– I don't know

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: mud plaster

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: wood is used for door ways, columns, ceilings, and the framework.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– I don't know

Notes: Grass is occasionally added to mud and stone mortar but I do not know if that is the case at Alchi.

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The murals and sculptures are painted with gold and mineral pigment.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The door frames and columns (on the veranda and in the interior) are made of intricately carved wood. Some temples also include wall paintings on the veranda.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The Dukhang and Sumtsek both include clay sculptures of deities in the central niche. These sculptures are affixed to the wall. For an extensive study of these clay sculptures, see Luczanits, Christian. *Buddhist Sculpture in Clay: Early Western Himalayan Art, late 10th to early 13th centuries* Chicago: Serindia, 2004.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The Dukhang and Alchi ceilings are painted to look like textiles.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Several of the temples, including the Dukhang and Sumtsek, include inscriptions.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: decoration on the ceiling is painted to look like textiles

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: In addition to the clay sculptures that belong to the overall iconographic program, practitioners have placed small scale metal sculptures in several of the temples' altars.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: The wooden door frames and columns are carved in relief

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: They depict Buddhas, bodhisattvas, and other deities.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The door frames and columns also include abstract motifs

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Mineral pigments are used to paint on mud-plaster walls.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The Alchi Sumtsek includes three monumental clay sculptures of the Maitreya (the future Buddha), Avalokitesvara (the bodhisattva of compassion) and Manjusri (the bodhisattva of wisdom). Their lower garments depict scenes from the life of Buddha and depictions of significant places in Kashmir.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Several temples and stupas include painted mandalas.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Reference: Denwood, Philip. ““temple and Rock Inscriptions of Alchi””. In *The Cultural History of Ladakh*, Volume 2, edited by David Snellgrove and Tadeusz Skorupski. Warminster: Aris and Philips, 1980.

Reference: Heller, Amy, and Shawo Khacham. “Tibetan Inscriptions at Alchi, Part 1: Towards a Reassessment of the Chronology”. *Tibetan Genealogies: Studies in Memoriam of Guge Tsering Gyalpo (1961-2015)*, 2018, 535-51.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Reference: Linrothe, Rob. "mapping the Iconographic Programme of the Sumtsek". In *Alchi, Ladakh's Hidden Buddhist Sactuary: The Sumtsek*, edited by Roger Goepper and Jaroslav Poncar. London: Serindia, 1996.

Reference: Goepper, Roger. "murals in the Early Temples of Alchi". In *On the Path to Void: Buddhist Art of the Tibetan Realm*, edited by Pratapaditya Pal. Mumbai: Marg, 1996.

Reference: Papa-Kalantari, Christiane. "the Ceiling Paintings of the Alchi Gsum Brtsegs: Problems of Style". In *Buddhist Art and Tibetan Patronage: Ninth to Fourteenth Centuries*, edited by Deborah Klimburg-Salter and Eva Allinger. Leiden: Brill, 2003.

Reference: Linrothe, Rob. "talisman, Reliquary and Instrument of Enlightenment: The Alchi Sumtsek as a Mandalic Site". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 22-29.

Reference: Goepper, Roger. "the 'great Stūpa' at Alchi". *Artibus Asiae* 53, no. 1/2 (1993): 111-43.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian, and Willibald Veit. "alchi and the Drigungpa School of Tibetan Buddhism: The Teacher Depiction in the Small Chörten at Alchi". In *Mei Shou Wan Nian (long Life Without End): Festschrift on the Occasion of Roger Goepper's 80th Birthday*, edited by Jeong-hee Lee-Kalisch and Antje Papist-Matsuo. Frankfurt: Peter Lang Verlag, 2006.

Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: In the Dukhang and Sumtsek, the eyes extend beyond the face. This is a distinctly Kashmiri convention and is evidence that the temples' painters were themselves from Kashmir.

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The many Buddhas and bodhisattvas are considered supernatural beings and are anthropomorphic.

Reference: Goepper, Roger. "akshobhya and His Paradise: Murals in the Dukhang of Alchi". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 16-21.

Reference: Kozicz, Gerald. "the Manjusri Lhakhang at Alchi: Creating Space for the Bodhisattva of Wisdom". *Journal of Comparative Cultural Studies in Architecture* 1 (2007): 21-27.

Reference: Allinger, Eva. "the Green Tara as Saviourness from the Eight Dangers in the Sumtsek at Alchi". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 40-44.

Reference: Rohilla, Jyoti. "green Tārā in the Wall Paintings of Alchi". In *Sacred Geography of Goddesses in South Asia: Essays in Memory of David Kinsley*, edited by Rana P.B. Singh. Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2010.

Reference: Tribe, Anthony. "mañjuśrī as Adibuddha: The Identity of an Eight-armed Form of Mañjuśrī Found in Early Western Himalayan Buddhist Art in the Light of Three Nāmasaṃgīti-related Texts". In *Śaivism and the Tantric Traditions: Essays in Honour of Alexis G.J.S. Sanderson*, edited by Dominic Goodall, Shaman Hatley, Harunaga Isaacson, and Srilata Raman. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: The mural paintings in Alchi's temples and stupas include representations of donors, devotees, Buddhist teachers, and other enlightened figures.

Reference: Alafouzo, Mario. "the Iconography and the Historical Context of the Drinking Scene in the Dukhang at Alchi, Ladakh.". In *Art and Architecture in Ladakh: Cross-cultural Transmissions in the Himalayas and Karakoram.* Leiden: Brill, 2014.

Reference: Linrothe, Rob, and Henrik Sorenson. "group Portrait: Mahasiddhas in the Alchi Sumtsek". In *Embodying Wisdom: Art, Text, and Interpretation in the History of Esoteric Buddhism*, edited by Rob Linrothe. Copenhagen: Seminar for Buddhist Studies, 2001.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian. "alchi and the Drigungpa School of Tibetan Buddhism: The Teacher Depiction in the Small Chorten at Alchi". In *Mei Shou Wan Nian (long Life Without End): Festschrift on the Occasion of Roger Goepfer's 80th Birthday*, edited by Jeong-hee Lee-Kalisch, Antje Papist-Matsuo, and Willibald Veit. Frankfurt: Peter Lang Verlag, 2006.

Reference: Flood, Finbarr B.. "mobility and Mutation: Iranian Hunting Themes in the Murals of Alchi, Western Himalayas". *South Asian Studies* 7 (1991): 21-35.

Reference: Flood, Finbarr B.. "cultural Cross-dressing". In *Objects of Translation: Material Culture and Medieval 'hindu-muslim' Encounter*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2009.

Reference: Flood, Finbarr B.. "A Turk in the Dukhang? Comparative Perspectives on Elite Dress in Medieval Ladakh and the Caucasus". In *Interaction in the Himalayas and Central Asia: Processes of Transfer, Translation, and Transformation in Art, Archaeology, Religion and Polity*.

Austria: Austrian Academy of Sciences Press, 2017.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: The Sumtsek contains monumental sculpture of the future Buddha Maitreya. Maitreya's dhoti (lower garment) depicts scenes from the life of the Buddha Sakyamuni.

Reference: Luczanits, Christian. "the Life of the Buddha in the Sumtsek". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 30-39.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Many of the temples' paintings depict mandalas, particularly from the Yoga Tantras

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: The site itself is not intended for funerary purposes. However, stupas harken back to the reliquary mounds in which the Buddha's remains were enshrined. Some stupas do contain the remains of highly venerated individuals. Many do not contain corporeal relics but nonetheless are imbued with the Buddha's or enlightened figure's presence.

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Notes: In Tibetan Buddhism there is a vast and diverse pantheon of deities but there is not one supreme deity. Tibetan Buddhist deities, such as those depicted at the Alchi complex, help devotees reach enlightenment in myriad ways. For example, there are deities who protect the Buddhist teachings, such as Mahakala who is depicted in the wall painting above the Sumtsek entrance. There are deities who act as intercessors, such as the goddess and bodhisattva Green Tara who considered a saviouress. Many Buddhas and bodhisattvas are the focus of meditations and yogic practices which generate realizations and insights regarding the true nature of reality. Most Tibetan Buddhists venerate and engage with numerous deities in a variety of ways, regardless if they are lay people, monastics, or other types of advanced practitioners.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there are numerous sculptures of Buddhas and bodhisattvas.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: In Tibetan Buddhism, giving material offerings to consecrated images of deities, living masters, and at sacred sites is ubiquitous. These offerings are both an act of devotion and generate merit and karmic benefits. Material offerings may include (but are not limited to) food items, butter lamps, incense, flowers (real or fake), offering scarves (called khata), money, and torma (sculptures made from barley flour).

Reference: Kohn, Richard J.. "an Offering of Torma". In *Religions of Tibet in Practice*, edited by Donald S. Lopez, Jr.. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1997.

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings may be valuable objects. In addition to monetary donations, Tibetan Buddhist auto/biographies of exemplary figures regularly mention offerings of expensive cloth (like silk brocade), small-scale sculptures, horses to expedite travel, and relics or other potent substances.

Reference: Ricard, Matthieu, trans.. "the Life of Shabkar: The Autobiography of a Tibetan Yogi". Translated by Matthieu Ricard. Ithaca, NY: Snow Lion Publications, 2001.

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings from daily life may include food items or flowers.

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Currently the site is maintained by the Archaeological Survey of India (AIS) who is required to conserve the site. There are no records about the complex's maintenance when it was built and actively in use.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: Currently the site is maintained by the Archaeological Survey of India (AIS) who is required to keep the site clean. There are no records about the complex's cleansing protocol when it was built and actively in use.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: Currently, maintenance is performed by the Archaeological Survey of India (AIS). There are no records pertaining to maintenance when it was built and actively in use. However, it is likely that this was the responsibility of the monastic communities who used the temples.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There have been 20th and 21st-century restorations and repairs. However, new temples and stupas were added between the 11th/13th and 14th centuries. Each changed the makeup of the Alchi complex.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage to sacred sites is common in Buddhism generally and Tibetan Buddhism specifically. Buddhist pilgrimages take many forms. There are formalized pilgrimages, such as visiting the "Eight Great Places" associated with the Buddha's major life events or circumambulating sacred mountains like Mount Kailash. Devotees may also travel to a specific sacred site because of its connection to a particular exemplar, its reputation as especially potent, or myriad other reasons. "The Alchi Group" (Alchi, Sumda Chung, and Mangyu) may have constituted its own pilgrimage route. Given the temples' geographic proximity, and their association with contemporary religious and political elites, exemplary artists, and iconographic foundations in the Yoga Tantras, they likely would be a major draw for local devotees. There are no extant records of visitors to the complex when it was active or pilgrimage guides for the Alchi group. However, local communities present the site as a consistent pilgrimage destination, particularly among Buddhist practitioners in the western Himalayas

Reference: Ranguin, Virginia C., and Dina Bangdel, eds.. "pilgrimage and Faith: Buddhism, Christianity, and Islam.". Edited by Virginia C. Ranguin and Dina Bangdel. Chicago: Serindia, 2010.

Reference: Huber, Toni. "the Cult of Pure Crystal Mountain: Popular Pilgrimage and Visionary Landscape in Southeast Tibet.". New York: Oxford University Press, 1999.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– I don't know

Notes: Presently, the Alchi complex is easily accessible by car, bus, or motorbike. These 20th and 21st century roads makes Alchi easily accessible for tourists, pilgrims, and local villagers alike. The other two temples in "The Alchi Group" are not accessible by motorable roads. However, for local devotees, all three temples in "The Alchi Group" could be reached by foot in 1-2 days using well-established routes through the mountainous terrain.

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Yes

Notes: The site is not currently in use except as a pilgrimage site and tourist draw. However, rituals would've taken place when it was regularly in use.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

Notes: The temples themselves do not have space for large-scale rituals so it seems unlikely. However, there is little concrete evidence regarding how they were used.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Currently, there is always one monk who resides at Alchi. These monks usually reside there for a period of two years before being replaced by another. There would have been religious specialists present full time when the site was in regular use.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: These specialists are monks.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Primarily they would have been from a western Himalayan ethnic group or central Tibetans.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Currently, the site is maintained by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI). There are no historical records regarding the complex's maintenance when it was in regular use, however it can be assumed that the monastic community was responsible for this work.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Many monasteries keep administrative records, such as a register of resident monastics, material holdings, and finances. In the case of the Alchi complex, no such records survive.

Reference: Sullivan, Brenton. "building a Religious Empire: Tibetan Buddhism, Bureaucracy, and the Rise of the Gelukpa.". Pennsylvania : University of Pennsylvania Press, 2021.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Typically, monasteries have their own collections of canonical Tibetan Buddhist texts. The canon comprises the teachings of the Buddha (the Kangyur) and commentaries on the teachings (Tengyur). There are copies of these canonical texts at Alchi but they date to the 20th century. There are no extant texts from the period when Alchi complex was in active use. In addition to the Tibetan canon, there are the Tibetan Buddhist tantras. "Tantra" refers to a category of Buddhist practice and the diverse group of texts that this is based on. Scholars continue to debate how to define tantra, when it emerged as an established form of Buddhist practice, and which texts fall into this category. In general, tantra is considered more esoteric, includes a wider pantheon of deities, and involves advanced meditations and yogic practices. There is no evidence regarding whether or not tantric texts were kept at Alchi. However, much of the temples' iconography (especially the Dukhang and Sumtsek) stems from a group of texts

known as the "Yoga Tantra."

Reference: Weinberger, Steven Neal. "the Significance of Yoga Tantra and the Compendium of Principles (tattvasamgraha Tantra) Within Tantric Buddhism in India and Tibet." PhD. dissertation, 2003.

Reference: White, David Gordon, ed.. "tantra in Practice". Edited by David Gordon White. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2018.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In Tibetan Buddhism, teachings and practices must be studied in conjunction with a qualified teacher.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

Notes: The Dukhang and Sumtsek iconographical plans incorporate concepts and practice supports from certain tantras. For example, both temples contain wall paintings of mandalas described in the Yoga Tantras. This includes the Dharmadhātu and Sarvavid mandalas. In addition, clay sculptures in the central niche of each temple are arranged in the form of the Vajradhātu mandala.

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The Dukhang's depiction of Buddha Akṣobhya's Abhirati paradise is paired with an excerpt from the Akṣobhyavyūha sutra. This text, like all sutras, are attributed to the Buddha's direct teachings. The Akṣobhyavyūha sutra describes the form, function, and meaning of Akṣobhya's paradise.

Reference: Goepper, Roger. "akshobhya and His Paradise: Murals in the Dukhang of Alchi". *Orientalia* 30, no. 1 (1999): 16–21.

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